

Prevalence of Serum Vitamin D Levels in the Iraqi Population: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Vitamin D deficiency in children causes rickets. It prevents children from reaching their maximum bone mass and genetic height. Abnormal mineralization of the collagen matrix in bone, known as osteomalacia, occurs in adults with vitamin D deficiency. **Aim:** The aim of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of serum vit. D levels in the Iraqi population. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study collected data from October 2024 to January 2025. Data was collected by directly interviewing the participants, the time needed for each interview was 10-15 minutes and screening for vit. D level by measuring serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D (23[OH]D) concentration as a part of their routine laboratory tests. **Results:** The majority of individuals in this group are deficient in vitamin D3 (4.6%), with very few in the insufficient and sufficient categories (0.6% each). Primary education: A significant percentage of individuals in this group are deficient (13.4%), with 3.2% in the insufficient category and 1.2% in the sufficient category. Secondary education: This group has a relatively higher proportion of deficient individuals (23%), with 8.8% being insufficient and 4.6% being sufficient. College: The deficient category is most prevalent in this group (25%), with 6.8% insufficient and 4.4% sufficient. Higher education: This group has the lowest proportion of deficient individuals (2.4%), with 0.8% insufficient and 0.6% sufficient. Urban residents: A larger proportion of urban residents are deficient in vitamin D3 (41.4%), with fewer individuals categorized as insufficient (8%) or sufficient (4.4%). Rural residents: A smaller proportion of rural residents are deficient (27%), with a higher percentage categorized as insufficient (12.2%) and sufficient (7%). Individuals with chronic conditions (Yes): A significant proportion are deficient in vitamin D3 (20.6%), with smaller percentages classified as insufficient (3.8%) or sufficient (1.6%). Individuals without chronic conditions (No): A larger proportion are deficient (47.8%), with a higher percentage classified as insufficient (16.4%) and sufficient (9.8%). **Conclusion:** There was no statistically significant association between vitamin D levels and educational attainment, suggesting that vitamin D deficiency affects people in all educational groups. A significant association was found between place of residence and vitamin D levels. Urban dwellers had a higher prevalence of deficiency than rural dwellers. The association between the presence of chronic diseases and vitamin D levels was statistically significant.

More Information

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Introduction

Vitamin D deficiency is associated with a range of adverse health outcomes, including impaired bone development and an increased risk of numerous common and serious illnesses. These include certain cancers, cardiovascular diseases, type 1 diabetes, and various autoimmune disorders [1,2]. Often referred to as the “sunshine vitamin”, vitamin D is synthesised in the skin upon exposure to sunlight. Its primary physiological role is to regulate serum calcium levels within the normal range, which is critical for musculoskeletal health [3].

In children, vitamin D deficiency can lead to rickets, a condition characterised by impaired bone mineralisation, which can hinder attainment of peak bone mass and genetically determined height. In adults, insufficient vitamin D results in osteomalacia, a condition where the collagen matrix of bone is poorly mineralised. This compromised matrix is structurally weak, heightening the risk of fractures. The inadequately mineralised bone exerts pressure on the periosteum—a pain-sensitive membrane—resulting in bone aches, a frequent symptom in individuals with vitamin D deficiency. Additionally, the deficiency is linked to muscle weakness and widespread musculoskeletal pain. It is estimated that 40% to 60% of individuals presenting with generalised myalgia and bone discomfort have underlying vitamin D deficiency [4].

Globally, both vitamin D deficiency (serum levels < 20 ng/mL) and insufficiency (levels between 20 and 30 ng/mL) are widespread concerns. High-risk populations include pregnant women, individuals of African or Hispanic descent, obese adults and children. In the United States, vitamin D deficiency affects approximately 50% of children aged 1 to 5 years and up to 70% of those aged 6 to 11 years. Contributing factors include increasing rates of obesity, declining milk consumption, and widespread use of sun protection measures [5].

Vitamin D exists in two primary forms: vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol) and vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol). Vitamin D₂ is typically derived from plant and fungal sources in the diet, while vitamin D₃ is obtained either through consumption of animal-based foods or synthesised in the skin via the photoconversion of 7-dehydrocholesterol upon adequate exposure to ultraviolet B (UVB) radiation. Effective dermal synthesis of vitamin D is generally only possible when the solar elevation angle exceeds 45 degrees [6,7].

There is ongoing debate regarding the optimal serum concentration of 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D]. According to the Endocrine Society, levels below 30 ng/mL indicate deficiency, with a preferred range of 40–60 ng/mL. In contrast, the National Institutes of

Health defines deficiency as a level below 20 ng/mL, with some experts categorising levels between 12–19 ng/mL as insufficient and levels under 12 ng/mL as severely deficient [8].

To achieve and maintain adequate levels of vitamin D, the Endocrine Society recommends daily intakes of 400–1,000 IU for infants under one year of age, 600–1,000 IU for children and adolescents aged 1 to 18 years, and 1,500–2,000 IU for adults. Despite variations in recommendations, many experts agree that serum 25(OH)D levels below 20 ng/mL (50 nmol/L) indicate vitamin D deficiency [9].

Methodology

Study population and sampling technique

In this cross-sectional study, a sample of 500 people was randomly selected from those who visited the Alkarama Teaching Hospital. Direct interviews were conducted using a questionnaire specifically designed for the study.

Subjects and Methods

A cross sectional study from The data collecting period spanned from September 2024 to January 2025. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews with participants, lasting 10-15 minutes each, approximately four days a week (Sunday to Wednesday) from 9am to 1pm.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analysed using SPSS version 24 computer software (Statistical Package for Social Sciences), with categorical variables presented as frequencies and percentages. Figures have been used where appropriate. Authors also used the chi-square test.

Results

Association Between Serum Vitamin D₃ Levels and Educational Attainment

Table 1 presents the outcomes of a Chi-square test conducted to assess the relationship between serum vitamin D₃ levels and participants' educational status.

- **Illiterate individuals:** The majority within this group exhibited vitamin D₃ deficiency (4.6%), while only a small proportion fell into the insufficient and sufficient categories (0.6% each).
- **Primary education:** A considerable proportion of individuals in this category were vitamin D₃ deficient (13.4%), with 3.2% classified as insufficient and 1.2% as sufficient.
- **Secondary education:** This group displayed a relatively higher rate of deficiency (23%), with 8.8% of individuals being insufficient and 4.6% being sufficient.
- **College education:** The prevalence of deficiency was highest in this category (25%), while 6.8% were insufficient and 4.4% sufficient.
- **Higher education:** Participants with higher education had the lowest prevalence of deficiency

(2.4%), with 0.8% classified as insufficient and 0.6% as sufficient. These findings suggest a potential inverse relationship between educational attainment and vitamin D₃

deficiency, with individuals of higher educational status displaying lower rates of deficiency.

Table 1. Statistical Test for Association between Serum Vitamin D3 Levels (ng/ml) and Educational Attainment

Variables		Serum Vitamin D3 Level (ng/ml)			Chi-square test	P value
		Deficient (<20ng/mL)	Insufficient (20-29 ng/mL)	Sufficient (≥30 ng/mL)		
Education state	Illiterate	23 (4.6%)	3 (0.6%)	3 (0.6%)	7.533	0.480
	Primary education	67 (13.4%)	16 (3.2%)	6 (1.2%)		
	Secondary education	115 (23%)	44 (8.8%)	23 (4.6%)		
	College	125 (25%)	34 (6.8%)	22 (4.4%)		
	Higher education	12 (2.4%)	4 (0.8%)	3 (0.6%)		
Total		342 (68.4%)	101 (20.2%)	57 (11.4%)		

Note: * Significant association between groups (p value <0.05)

Figure 1: The Association between Serum Vitamin D3 Levels (ng/ml) and Educational Attainment

Association Between Serum Vitamin D₃ Levels and Place of Residence

Table 2 displays the results of a Chi-square test used to determine the association between serum vitamin D₃ levels and place of residence (urban versus rural).

- **Urban residents:** A larger proportion of urban participants were deficient in vitamin D₃ (41.4%), with 8% classified as insufficient and 4.4% as sufficient.

- **Rural residents:** In contrast, a lower proportion of rural individuals were vitamin D₃ deficient (27%), while higher percentages were found to be insufficient (12.2%) and sufficient (7%). These results indicate that rural residents tend to have more favourable vitamin D₃ profiles compared to their urban counterparts, potentially due to increased sun exposure or lifestyle differences related to outdoor activity.

Table 2: Statistical Test for Association between Serum Vitamin D3 Levels (ng/ml) and Place of Residence

Variables		Serum Vitamin D3 Level (ng/ml)			Chi-square test	P value
		Deficient (<20ng/mL)	Insufficient (20-29 ng/mL)	Sufficient (≥30 ng/mL)		
Residence	Urban	207 (41.4%)	40 (8%)	22 (4.4%)	19.715	<0.001*

	Rural	135 (27%)	61 (12.2%)	35 (7%)		
Total		342 (68.4%)	101 (20.2%)	57 (11.4%)		

Note: * Significant association between groups (p value <0.05)

Figure 2: The Association Between Serum Vitamin D3 Levels (ng/ml) and Residence

Association Between Serum Vitamin D₃ Levels and Presence of Chronic Conditions

Table 3 displays the results of a Chi-square test examining the relationship between serum vitamin D₃ levels and the presence of chronic conditions (Yes vs No) in the study population.

- **Participants with chronic conditions:** A notable proportion of this group were vitamin D₃ deficient (20.6%), while smaller percentages were classified as insufficient (3.8%) or sufficient (1.6%).
- **Participants without chronic conditions:** A higher percentage were vitamin D₃ deficient (47.8%), with 16.4% deemed insufficient and 9.8% sufficient.

Table 3: Statistical Test for the Association Between Serum Vitamin D3 Levels (ng/ml) and Chronic Diseases

Variables		Serum Vitamin D3 Level (ng/ml)			Chi-square test	P value
		Deficient (<20ng/mL)	Insufficient (20-29 ng/mL)	Sufficient (≥30 ng/mL)		
Do you have chronic diseases?	Yes	103 (20.6%)	19 (3.8%)	8 (1.6%)	9.966	0.007*
	No	239 (47.8%)	82 (16.4%)	49 (9.8%)		
Total		342 (68.4%)	101 (20.2%)	57 (11.4%)		

Note: * Significant association between groups (p value <0.05)

Figure 5: The Association between Serum Vitamin D3 Levels (ng/ml) and Chronic Diseases

Discussion

The study's findings indicate that vitamin D deficiency (<20 ng/mL) is prevalent across all educational categories, with the highest proportion observed among individuals with college-level education (25%) and the lowest among those with higher education (2.4%). Despite this variation, the lack of a statistically significant association ($p = 0.480$) between education level and vitamin D status suggests that other factors—such as dietary habits, lifestyle, and sun exposure—may play a more substantial role. This observation is consistent with studies conducted in Middle Eastern populations, such as that by [10], which reported widespread vitamin D deficiency irrespective of educational attainment, often attributed to limited sun exposure and low dietary intake.

However, this finding contrasts with [11], who reported a positive correlation between higher education and greater awareness of vitamin D's health benefits, resulting in proactive measures such as supplementation and intentional sun exposure. Similarly, [12] highlighted the global nature of vitamin D deficiency, often independent of education level, especially in urbanised settings with restricted sunlight. [13] further pointed to cultural practices and a lack of fortified foods as significant contributors to deficiency in Arab populations. These findings highlight the need for targeted public health strategies that raise awareness and encourage preventive actions—such as safe sun exposure and dietary supplementation—across all educational strata.

The results from **Table 2** reveal a statistically significant association ($p < 0.001$) between vitamin D₃ status and place of residence. Urban dwellers exhibited a markedly higher prevalence of vitamin D deficiency (41.4%) compared to their rural counterparts (27%). In contrast, rural residents had greater proportions of individuals with insufficient (12.2%) and sufficient (7%) vitamin D levels than urban residents (8% and 4.4%, respectively). These findings suggest that urban lifestyles, characterised by reduced sun exposure due to indoor living, high-rise buildings, and air pollution, may increase the risk of vitamin D deficiency. In contrast, rural residents are likely to benefit from increased outdoor activity and sun exposure, promoting endogenous vitamin D synthesis. This pattern aligns with the findings of [14], who reported higher vitamin D levels in rural populations, largely attributed to lifestyle factors. However, it diverges from [11], who emphasised the role of vitamin D supplementation and access to fortified foods, typically more available in urban settings. These findings reinforce the importance of context-specific interventions, particularly in urban areas, including awareness campaigns, supplementation programmes, and policies encouraging safe sun exposure.

Results from Table 3 demonstrate a statistically significant association ($p = 0.007$) between the presence of chronic conditions and serum vitamin D₃ levels. Interestingly, individuals with chronic illnesses showed a lower prevalence of vitamin D deficiency (20.6%) than those without chronic conditions (47.8%). They also had lower rates of insufficiency (3.8% vs 16.4%) and sufficiency (1.6% vs 9.8%). This somewhat unexpected trend may be explained by greater medical oversight among individuals with chronic illnesses, which often includes routine screening for micronutrient deficiencies and a higher likelihood of supplementation. This interpretation is supported by studies such as [15], who demonstrated that individuals with chronic conditions frequently undergo monitoring for vitamin D levels. Likewise, [16] highlighted the role of regular health assessments in maintaining adequate vitamin D status among such patients.

However, these findings contrast with those of [13], who observed higher rates of deficiency among chronically ill individuals, potentially due to reduced mobility, limited sun exposure, or inadequate nutrition. Overall, the present findings underscore the importance of broad-based public health measures aimed at improving vitamin D status, particularly among individuals without chronic health conditions, who may be less likely to undergo regular screening or take preventive action.

Conclusion

This study highlights the widespread prevalence of vitamin D deficiency across varying demographic and socio-environmental groups. The key findings are as follows:

- **Educational attainment:** No statistically significant association was found between education level and vitamin D status, suggesting that deficiency affects individuals across all educational backgrounds. Nonetheless, those with higher education exhibited slightly better vitamin D levels.
- **Place of residence:** A significant association was observed, with urban residents showing a greater prevalence of vitamin D deficiency than rural residents. This disparity may be attributed to reduced sun exposure and environmental factors in urban settings.
- **Chronic health conditions:** A statistically significant association was identified between vitamin D status and the presence of chronic conditions. Contrary to expectations, individuals with chronic conditions demonstrated better vitamin D profiles, likely due to increased medical attention and supplementation.

These results reinforce the view that vitamin D deficiency remains a pressing public health concern, shaped by a complex interplay of lifestyle, environmental, and health-related factors. Addressing this issue requires multifaceted interventions, including

targeted awareness campaigns, widespread supplementation initiatives, and the promotion of behaviours that support healthy vitamin D levels.

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